

What is Important to You?

Luke 16:14-18

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14 Now the Pharisees, who were lovers of money, were listening to all these things and were ridiculing Him. **15** And He said to them, “You are the ones who justify yourselves in the sight of people, but God knows your hearts; because that which is highly esteemed among people is detestable in the sight of God.

16 “The Law and the Prophets *were proclaimed* until John *came*; since that time the gospel of the kingdom of God has been preached, and everyone is forcing his way into it. **17** “But it is easier for heaven and earth to pass away than for one stroke of a letter of the Law to fail.

18 “Everyone who divorces his wife and marries another commits adultery, and he who marries one who is divorced from a husband commits adultery.

Occasionally we look at Scripture and wonder why these stories are put together the way they are. We must remember that Scripture is divinely inspired. When it comes to the Gospels of Jesus Christ, it is also important to remember that most of them were written 30 to 60 years after his life. It is truly spectacular—and a great blessing for us as followers of Christ—that his words and actions have been passed down to us. We sometimes forget to thank those who gave their lives to ensure that the words of Christ reached future generations. We rarely think about that, but perhaps at times we should pause and simply contemplate it.

This Scripture passage comes from the Gospel of Luke, chapter 16, verses 14 through 18. This section begins with Jesus criticizing a group of Pharisees who are described as lovers of money. If they loved money so much, why were they listening to him? Scripture often tells us that the Pharisees and religious leaders wanted to trap Jesus into committing some form of blasphemy. I am not saying that this is untrue, and toward

the end of the Gospels it certainly seems apparent. However, the Pharisees were also products of their culture. To fully understand the original meaning of Scripture, we must ask what people in Jesus' day believed and valued. To accomplish that, we need to connect the culture of the time with the words we find in the Gospels.

Debate and conversation were key elements of religious education and training. One did not study Scripture alone but always with a partner. People questioned the Scriptures as a way of trying to understand their meaning. Multiple interpretations were not only possible but expected. When you discuss Scripture with someone who has a different perspective, you begin to see new possibilities yourself. Unfortunately, this practice is not very common in churches today. It may happen in some Bible study settings, but in my experience, many people prefer to hear the same familiar story—the one that comforts them.

I once heard someone say that many people come to church hoping that the “Jesus bus” will pick them up one day and carry them off to heaven. They believe they don't have to do anything to get on the bus except show up on Sunday morning, because Jesus knows exactly when worship starts and will arrive on time. You may chuckle at that idea, but I assure you—it's true.

I once visited a man in the hospital after receiving a call from the chaplain's office saying he wanted a visit. His name was identical to that of a church member, so I went immediately. Of course, I would have gone regardless, since he specifically requested a visit from a pastor. When I entered the room, I looked at him and said, “Who are you?” Years earlier, he had been baptized in the church I served, but that was the last time he ever attended. I asked him why church membership mattered to him after being absent for decades. He told me that when he died, he needed to be buried by a pastor so that he could go to heaven. I didn't argue with him, especially since he was in the hospital, but it made me wonder how many people think that way.

So when Jesus speaks about Pharisees who love money, perhaps we should look inward and ask ourselves what laws—or priorities—we live by. Is God your first love? We sometimes joke that God is from the state of Missouri, where people want proof: “Show me.” So how do we show God that we love him more than anything else in this world? We must remember that everything we have comes from God. God created the heavens and the earth; therefore, everything we touch comes from God.

Sporadically we forget that even our physical bodies are creations of God. Think about this for a moment: at some point in your life, you may have drunk a water molecule that once passed through Jesus’ body. You may also have breathed in an oxygen molecule that Jesus once inhaled. Everything in this world recycles itself, so it is entirely possible. It’s a striking idea when you think about it—that we are physically connected to Christ in ways we rarely consider.

Jesus ushered in the kingdom of God. In this passage from Luke, Jesus tells us that John the Baptist is the last of the prophets. In Judea, there had not been a prophet for over 400 years. Your Bible likely skips over those years. When Martin Luther translated the Bible, he chose not to include texts that he could not find in Hebrew or Greek. This resulted in the exclusion of about 17 books, which we now call the Apocrypha. These books cover those “missing” 400 years that the Protestant church often mentions. They are important texts and help us understand how God worked through the Jewish people to prepare the way for the Messiah.

Returning to Luke, Jesus tells us that the age of the prophets ended with John the Baptist. Yet Jesus himself is also a prophet—indeed, the ultimate prophet, the Messiah. Through Luke’s Gospel, Jesus is sharing with us that we no longer need to look for another Messiah or prophet. He has already come.

It is essential to remember that there were many expressions of Christianity emerging in the ancient world. Jesus did not provide detailed instructions for creating a new

religion because that was not his goal. He came to reform Judaism and extend it to the world. It was Jesus' followers—especially Paul—who shaped Christianity into a distinct religion. Paul's letters give us much of Christian theology, ritual, and structure. In many ways, modern Christianity is “Pauline Christianity.” Other groups, such as the Gnostics and the Ebionites, also believed Jesus was the Messiah but understood him differently. Many such groups arose in the second and third centuries CE and were eventually suppressed after Christianity became the official religion of the Roman Empire.

So when Jesus says that the kingdom of God is upon us, he is declaring that the final prophet has come and gone and that God's Messiah has been revealed to the world. Occasionally it is difficult to see that kingdom fully realized. But it is up to each of us who call ourselves Christians and followers of Jesus Christ to help bring the kingdom of heaven to all people. If everyone embraced the hope and grace offered by Jesus Christ, we would not be plagued by war and violent division. We would strive to love God and love our neighbors, just as Jesus taught us in the Gospels. And if you ever wonder how God wants us to live—and you would rather not read the entire Torah to figure it out—all you need to do is read the Gospels.

Amen.